

THE SIGNIFICANCE AND EFFICIENCY OF NEW INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Mavlanova Feruzakhan Zafarjanovna

Tashkent Chemical Technology Institute Department of Foreign languages,
Assistant teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11219037>

Annotation: The article talks about the importance of using new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of English, and all the possibilities of the student are analyzed, taking into account the complexity of mastering the subject. Also, examples of new methods in language development are given and its importance is revealed.

Key words: English language, methodology, science, method, lesson, student, pedagogue, educational system, interactive methodology.

Introduction.

"President's prize will be established for schools that have achieved high performance in foreign languages" - Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In fact, it is the task of us pedagogues to create school lessons and textbooks that can meet the standards of countries recognized by the world through the development of a foreign language. Gladly, the fact that those who can speak English are found in the first grade of the school is a sign of the hard work of English language experts being absorbed into the system. Especially, the number of students achieving international degrees in a foreign language is increasing day by day. Besides our national university, we are also pleased that more than seven out of one student is a student in the world's top 1000 universities.

By the way, mastering science is a somewhat complicated process. Mastering a foreign language as well as one's own language depends on the skill of the pedagogue. The use of new pedagogical methods is also important and effective. Compared to the traditional lesson, the student's mastery rate is higher in the lesson conducted using new technologies. Below we will talk about the essence of such new pedagogical methods and their practical application.

In most literature, the most popular interactive educational methods are "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blister survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Problem-based learning". " is noted. According to the data, interactive educational strategies include "Brainstorming", "Boomerang", "Gallery", "Zig-zag", "Zine-Zine", "Muzyorar", "Rotastia", "Snowball" methods. enters. When separating interactive educational strategies from the composition of interactive educational methods, the approach to organizing group work is based on the fact

that in a certain sense it is compared to strategic planning. In fact, these strategies are more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

Interactive graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Conceptual table", "Venn diagram", "T-table", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", "How?" and b. The separation of interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that the main ideas are expressed in written form in various graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more related to interactive educational methods.

Let's analyze some of the new interactive methods below.

Discussion.

"Brainstorming" method

This method ensures the students' activity in the training process, encourages them to think freely and frees them from the inertia of the same thinking, collects various ideas on a specific topic, as well as the initial process of solving creative tasks. serves to learn to overcome the thoughts that appeared in the stage.

The main principle and condition of the "thought attack" method is to absolutely prohibit criticism of the opinion expressed by each participant of the training, and to encourage any jokes and jokes. The purpose of this is to ensure the free participation of students in the training process. The use of this method in the educational process depends on the teacher's pedagogical skills and breadth of thinking.

When using the "brainstorming" method, the number of students should not exceed 10-15 people.

"General brainstorming" method.

The method serves to create conditions for students to come up with new ideas. Each group of 5 or 6 students is given a different assignment or creative task that needs to be solved within 15 minutes. After the successful solution within the specified time, one of the group members will give a report about it.

The information given by the group (*the solution of the assignment or creative task*) is discussed and evaluated by the teacher and other group members. At the end of the lesson, the teacher will announce the best and most unique answers to the assigned tasks or creative tasks. During the training, the activities of the group members are evaluated according to the level of their participation.

"6x6x6" method.

With the help of the "6x6x6" method, it is possible to solve a certain task or problem by involving 36 students in a certain activity at the same time, as well as to determine the capabilities of each member of the group, to learn their views. In the training organized on the basis of this method, 6 groups with 6 participants in each discuss the problem raised by the teacher. At the end of the specified time, the teacher reorganizes 6 groups. Each of the newly formed groups will have one representative from the previous 6 groups. The members of the newly formed group report to their teammates the conclusion presented by their group as a solution to the problem and discuss these solutions together.

The advantages of the "6x6x6" method are as follows:

- encourages each member of the group to be active;
- ensures the expression of personal views by them;
- develops the skills of listening to the opinions of other members of the group;
- being able to summarize several ideas being advanced, and also teaches to defend one's opinion.

The most important thing is that during each short time (20 minutes) the participants of the training will act as a participant in the discussion, and as a listener, and as a speaker.

This method can be used in several groups consisting of 5, 6, 7 and 8 students. However, when the "6x6x6" method is used among large groups, it is necessary to increase the time. Because in such training, a lot of time is required for discussion and information. When the method in question is used, there is an opportunity to do one or more subjects in the training.

The use of the "6x6x6" method in the educational process requires the teacher to be active, have pedagogical skills, and also have the ability to form groups in accordance with the purpose. Improper formation of groups can cause tasks or tasks not to be solved correctly. Using this method, training is organized in the following order:

- Before the lesson, the teacher places 6 chairs around 6 tables.
- Students are divided into 6 groups by the teacher. When dividing the students into groups, each seat is named, and those who received the name slips sit in their seats.
- After the students have settled down, the teacher announces the topic of the lesson and gives certain tasks to the groups. A certain time is set and the discussion process is organized.

➤ The teacher monitors the activity of the groups, gives advice to the group members in the necessary places, gives guidance, and after making sure that the tasks given by the groups have been solved correctly, the discussions from the groups asks them to finish.

➤ When the time for the discussion is over, the teacher re-forms the groups. Each of the newly formed groups will have one representative from the previous 6 groups. The members of the newly formed group report to their teammates the conclusion presented by their group as a solution to the problem and discuss these solutions together.

Conclusion.

Pedagogical technology is essentially organized with the help of forms, methods and tools, increases the effectiveness of pedagogical activity and determines mutual cooperation between teachers. In addition, it ensures students' acquisition of thorough knowledge of educational subjects forms independent, free and creative thinking skills in students. At the same time, necessary conditions are created for students to realize their potential. It is also necessary to guarantee the priority of democratic and humanitarian ideas in the pedagogical process.

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